

EFFECT OF THE CONTENT OF CFRP ON THE BEHAVIOR OF CALL

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ABSTRACT

A new type of hybrid composite, Carbon fiber/epoxy resin/AL alloy Laminate (CALL) is presented in this paper. The manufacture processing of CALL is briefly described. The effect of volume content of carbon fiber reinforced plastics (CFRP) on the thermal, mechanical, and wear behavior of CALL is studied.

INTRODUCTION

An advanced and promising structural material, fiber reinforced resin/metal laminate is being developed.

A series of research work on Aramid fiber reinforced AL alloy Laminate (ARALL) were carried out by Department of Aerospace Engineering of Delft University of Technology, Netherland in cooperation with the Fokker Aircraft Company, Dutch National Aerospace Laboratory, ENKA, 3M, and Alcoa Center U.S.A.¹⁻⁷ It was reported that ARALL laminate possessed excellent fatigue property, high tensile strength as composites and impact resistance, easy machining as metal. Four ARALL laminate product forms with high strength, increased formability, high toughness, and high temperature properties, respectively, have been available.⁸⁻¹¹ It was predicted that by the 1990s 5-10% of the airframe or 10-15% of the aerospace sheet metal market may be taken by ARALL.^{12,13} Based on the outstanding properties of carbon fiber reinforced plastics (CFRP) carbon fiber/epoxy/AL Laminate (CALL) was treated with for its low specific gravity, low thermal expansion, high strength, and long fatigue life. The applications of CALL to beam in England¹⁴ and to pneumatic actuator in Japan¹⁵ were reported. Glass fiber/epoxy/AL Laminate (GLALL) was also studied.

The effect of volume content of CFRP on the thermal, mechanical, and wear behavior of CALL is focused on in this paper.

EXPERIMENTAL

1. Raw Materials and Preparation of CALL

The Al alloy used in this work was LY_{12CZ} supplied as various thickness sheets with a composition of 3.8-4.9% Cu, 1.2-1.8% Mg, 0.3-0.9% Mn and the rest Al. Carbon fiber and carbon woven fabric were both supplied by Shanghai Carbon Factory. Epoxy resin 648# and curing agent 594# were both supplied by Shanghai Resin Factory. A block diagram of preparation of CALL is shown in Fig.1.

2. Valuation of Properties of CALL

The thermal expansion coefficient of CALL was measured from room temperature to 200°C using a thermo-analyzer of type D7-30. The mechanical behavior of CALL was tested using an electron tensile tester of type DCS-2000 at a rate of 1 mm/min with the spans of 20mm and 80mm for shear

test and flexure test, respectively. The wear test of CALL was carried out using a wear machine of type M-200 at a load of 5 kg and a speed of 200rpm against high carbon steel counterface with or without oil lubrication. After 60 minutes of sliding, the wear was measured from mass lost of CALL.

Fig.1 The block diagram of preparation of CALL

3. Examination of the Morphology of CALL

The microstructure of CALL and CFRP was observed using a metallurgical microscope of type DME-1. The examination of failed specimens after shear test or tensile test was carried out using an optical microscope of type XTL-1 and a scanning electron microscope of type DSM-1, respectively.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. Examination of the Microstructure of CALL

Fig.2 The microstructure of CALL composed of unidirectional carbon fiber 79.5x3

The microstructure of CALL composed of unidirectional carbon fiber/epoxy/Al alloy is shown in Fig.2 using a metallurgical microscope with a magnification of 79.5. In Fig. 2 the bright area is the component of Al alloy and the dark area is the component of CFRP where the white spots are carbon fibers and the black background is the matrix of epoxy resin. It is found that the surface of Al alloy and the surface of carbon fiber are both covered by epoxy matrix throughout.

The microstructure of CALL composed of carbon woven fabric is shown in Fig.3(a) and 3(b) with the magnification of 52 and 210, respectively. Like Fig.2, the bright and dark areas represent the components of Al alloy and CFRP, It is clear that two bundles of carbon fiber are woven perpendicularly. The perpendicular carbon fiber and parallel carbon fiber are entirely surrounded by epoxy matrix. Therefore, a fair bonding state between Al alloy or carbon fiber (fabric) and resin matrix can be obtained from the processing shown in Fig.1.

(a)

(b)

Fig.3 The microstructure of CALL composed of woven carbon fabric
(a) 52x3 (b) 210x3

2. Effect of the Content of CFRP on the Specific Gravity of CALL

Fig.4 The relationship between d of CALL and v (%) of CFRP

Low specific gravity of Al alloy is important for its application to structural material of airplane or other aircrafts. The specific gravity of CFRP is much lower than Al alloy, there the specific gravity of CALL is lower than Al alloy. Moreover, CALL can be designed to a certain value of specific gravity by controlling the content of CFRP. The relationship between the specific gravity of CALL and the volume content of CFRP is shown in Fig.4. It is obvious that the specific gravity of CALL decreases with an increase in the volume content of CFRP.

3. Effect of the Content of CFRP on the Thermal Expansion of CALL

The thermal expansion coefficients of CALL with various volume contents of CFRP composed of unidirectional carbon fiber are listed in Table 1. As the thermal expansion coefficient of carbon fiber is very low, the thermal expansion coefficient of CFRP is low, only 3% of the corresponding value of Al alloy.^{17,18} The thermal expansion coefficient of CALL is low and decreases with an increase in volume content of CFRP. It is found that the measured values are close to the values calculated according to the formula of thermal expansion coefficient of composites.

Table 1 Effect of CFRP content on thermal expansion coefficient of CALL

CFRP v%	α of CALL		$\times 10^{-5}/^{\circ}\text{C}$
	from measurement	from literature	from calculation
0		2.40 ¹	
30	1.91		1.33
42	1.78		1.02
65	0.46		0.56
100		0.07 ¹⁸	

4. Effect of the Content of CFRP on the Mechanical Behavior of CALL

Fig.5 Effect of the content of CFRP on the shear strength of CALL

Effect of the volume content of CFRP on the tensile, shear, and flexure strength of CALL are shown in Fig.5, 6, and 7, respectively. It is found that when the volume content of CFRP is low (15%) the mechanical behavior of CALL is worse than Al alloy. This result may be attributed to two factors. On one hand, the existence of interface between Al alloy and CFRP may be harmful to the mechanical behavior of CALL. On the other hand, the volume content of CFRP is too low to reinforce the hybrid. However, an increase in the content of CFRP enhanced the mechanical properties of CALL. As the content of CFRP increased from 15% to 55% the mechanical properties of CALL were improved. It is notable that

the tensile strength and shear strength of CALL composed of 55% CFRP are better than the corresponding values of Al alloy or CFRP due to the

Fig.6 Effect of the content of CFRP on the tensile strength of CALL

Fig.7 Effect of the content of CFRP on the flexure strength of CALL

composite effect. The interface effect can be confirmed by the microscopical examination of specimens after tensile test or shear test. The microphotos of CALL specimens after shear test were taken using an optical microscope are shown in Fig.8. The crack in Al alloy and the crack in CFRP are shown

Fig.8 The microphotos of CALL specimens after shear test
(a) (b) : 9.5 x 3 (c) : 6.3 x 3

in Fig.8(a) and 8(b) with a magnification of 9.5 x 3. The crack in the interface between Al alloy and CFRP is shown in Fig. 8(c) with a magnification of 6.3 x 3 and is obviously longer and wider than cracks in Al alloy and in CFRP. In fact, most failure of CALL specimens were started from interface crack. The microphotos of CALL specimens after tensile tests were taken using a scanning electron microscope and are shown in Fig.9. The dark grooves shown in Fig.9(a) and 9(b) are interface cracks.

Fig.9 The microphotos of CALL specimens after tensile test
(a) (b): 100 x 3 (c) : 3000 x 3

The microphotos of cross section of fracture CFRP is shown in Fig.9(c). It clearly shows cracked carbon fibers and the caves where carbon fibers were pulled out. The comparison of mechanical behavior of CALL with ARALL and GLALL is listed in Table 2.

Table 2 A comparison of mechanical behavior of CALL with ARALL and GLALL

Composites	Tensile Strength MPa	Flexural Strength MPa	Shear Strength MPa
CALL ⁸	790	1250	65
ARALL ⁸	800	738	/
ARALL ¹⁶	852	863	32
GLALL ¹⁶	478	869	42

It is found that the tensile strength of CALL is comparable with ARALL and is higher than GLALL by a factor of 1.65. The shear strength and flexure strength of CALL are both better than ARALL and GLALL. It is concluded that CALL is a promising materials.

5. Effect of the Content of CFRP on the Wear Rate of CALL

The wear rates of CALL composed of several contents of CFRP are listed on Table 3. The wear was measured by weight. According to the relationship between specific gravity of CALL and CFRP content shown in Fig.2, the mass lost of CALL was converted to volume lost of CALL so as to compare the wear rate of CALL composed of different content of CFRP. Without oil lubrication the wear rate of CALL is not high and decreases with an increase in the content of CFRP, because carbon fiber is nearly a self-lubricating material. With oil lubrication the wear rate of CALL is low and is improved by increasing the content of CFRP.

Table 3 Effect of CFRP content on wear rate of CALL

CFRP V%	wear rate mm ³ /hr	
	with lubrication	without lubrication
29	3.05×10^{-3}	1.75
57	1.75×10^{-3}	1.20
81	1.50×10^{-3}	0.75

CONCLUSION

Low specific gravity, low thermal expansion, high strengths of tensile, shear, flexure, and low wear rate of CALL have been revealed. Moreover, these properties of CALL can be further improved by an increase in the volume content of CFRP. The above mechanical strengths of CALL of 55% CFRP are mostly better than the corresponding values of ARALL or GLALL.

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